

New species and new records in Cerithiopsidae and Newtoniellidae (Triphoroidea, Gastropoda) from the Azores and the South Azorean Seamount Chain

Nuevas especies y nuevas citas en Cerithiopsidae y Newtoniellidae (Triphoroidea, Gastropoda) de las Azores y de la cadena de montañas submarinas al sur del archipiélago

Serge GOFAS^{1, *}, André FREIWALD² & Leon HOFFMAN²

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ABSTRACT

This study is part of a broader inventory of bathyal molluscs from the Azores and South Azorean Seamount Chain. Herein a review was completed on taxa in the families Cerithiopsidae and Newtoniellidae, mostly represented in our material by empty shells. Twenty-one species are recorded, of which only five have a planktotrophic larval development. Six new species are described in Cerithiopsidae (*Cerithiopsis slikeri* n. sp., *Krachia cochleapex* n. sp., *K. trauseli* n. sp., *K. stilapex* n. sp., *K. meteoris* n. sp., *Onchodia tenuicula* n. sp.) and four species in Newtoniellidae (*Cerithiella seilaeformis* n. sp., *Eumetula bicarinata* n. sp., *E. fenestrata* n. sp., *Trituba azorica* n. sp.). *Cerithiella candela* Fernandes, Garofalo & Pimenta, 2015 is recorded from Meteor Seamount, for the first time outside the southwestern Atlantic. *Cerithiopsis fayalensis*, *Krachia* cf. *obeliscoides*, *Ektonos turbonilloides*, *Cerithiella metula*, *Cerithiella amblytera*, *Eumetula bouvieri* and *E. alicei*, previously known from the Azores, are recorded on the South Azorean Seamount Chain. Most species are represented in more than one seamount and around the Azores, and only *K. trauseli* and *T. azorica* appear restricted to the seamounts near the Azores; nevertheless, most new species are likely endemic to the study area.

RESUMEN

Este estudio forma parte de un inventario más amplio de moluscos batiales de las Azores y la cadena de montañas submarinas al sur de este archipiélago. Se completó una revisión de los taxones de las familias Cerithiopsidae y Newtoniellidae, representadas en su mayoría en nuestro material por conchas vacías. Se registran veintiuna especies, de las cuales solo cinco tienen un desarrollo larvario planctotrófico. Se describen seis nuevas especies en Cerithiopsidae (*Cerithiopsis slikeri* n. sp., *Krachia cochleapex* n. sp., *K. trauseli* n. sp., *K. stilapex* n. sp., *K. meteoris* n. sp., *Onchodia tenuicula* n. sp.) y cuatro especies en Newtoniellidae (*Cerithiella seilaeformis* n. sp., *Eumetula bicarinata* n. sp., *E. fenestrata* n. sp., *Trituba azorica* n. sp.). *Cerithiella candela* Fernandes, Garofalo & Pimenta, 2015 se cita del Banco Meteor, por primera vez fuera del Atlántico suroccidental.

¹ Departamento de Biología Animal, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, Málaga, Spain and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

² Marine Research Department, Senckenberg am Meer, Südstrand 40, Wilhelmshaven, Germany

* Corresponding author: Serge Gofas <sgofas@uma.es>

Cerithiopsis fayalensis, *Krachia* cf. *obeliscoides*, *Ektonos turbonilloides*, *Cerithiella metula*, *Cerithiella amblytera*, *Eumetula bouvieri* y *E. alicei*, anteriormente conocidas de las Azores, se citan de las montañas submarinas al sur de estas. La mayoría de las especies están representadas en más de un monte submarino y alrededor de las Azores y solo *K. trauseli* y *T. azorica* aparecen restringidas a las montañas submarinas en el entorno de las Azores; sin embargo, es probable que la mayoría de las nuevas especies sean endémicas del área de estudio.

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KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Caenogastropoda, *Krachia*, *Onchodia*, *Cerithiella*, *Eumetula*, *Trituba*, Atlantic Ocean.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Caenogastropoda, *Krachia*, *Onchodia*, *Cerithiella*, *Eumetula*, *Trituba*, océano Atlántico.

INTRODUCTION

The molluscan fauna of the Azores and the North Atlantic seamounts south of the archipelago, has received renewed attention in a series of papers dealing with the taxonomy of several groups (see GOFAS, 2007 for a general account on the seamounts, and HOFFMAN *ET AL.*, 2020 for an overview of more recent papers). This paper addresses species in the families Cerithiopsidae and Newtoniellidae (Triphoroidea).

Species in Cerithiopsidae are spongi- vorous gastropods living in nearly all habitats where sponges live, from intertidal zones to bathyal depths in all oceans of the world. They form a taxonomically complex and large family with currently 39 genera and 993 accepted species (MOLLUSCABASE, 2022). Several reviews of genera in Cerithiopsidae have a regional scope (e. g. MARSHALL, 1978; CECALUPO & ROBBA, 2010; CECALUPO & PERUGIA, 2017) but no recent global review of the family was completed. Historical publications on species in the NE Atlantic and Mediterranean are plentiful and scattered in time. The Newtoniellidae are less well-known but allied and comprise 12 living genera with 119 accepted species worldwide (MOLLUSCABASE, 2022). Among these, the relict genus *Trituba* Jousseaume forms an important radiation in the North Atlantic seamounts (GOFAS, 2003).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A large material was collected during the Seamount 2 expedition, conducted in January/February 1993 by the first author with R/V *Le Suroit* and visiting the Great Meteor, Hyères, Irving, Plato, Atlantis and Tyro seamounts (69 dredge hauls and 16 beam trawl operations shallower than 1000 m, see GOFAS, 1993). In the Seamount cruises and other MNHN surveys, the coarse fractions were mostly sorted on board, and the finer fractions sieved on 5 mm, 2 mm, 1 mm and 0.5 mm sieves, and sorted under a stereomicroscope. The largest part of the collected material consisted of empty shells, most of them in the 1-5 mm size range.

The cruise M151 Athena was conducted in October 2018 by R/V *Meteor* and visited six seamount areas south of the Azores to investigate geology, oceanographic conditions and the biodiversity associated to deep-water coral habitats (FRANK, 2018). Refer to HOFFMAN & FREIWALD (2020) for a description of the sampling procedure. The term “Azorean seamounts” within this study refers to the group of all seamounts around and south of the Azores, southwards to the Meteor seamounts.

Holotypes are deposited in Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle (MNHN), Paris; paratypes are retained in MNHN and Senckenberg Naturmuseum (SMF),

Figure 1. Conventions used in shell descriptions. A. Apical view showing the options taken for whorl count and for rib count on a whorl. N: nucleus; P/T: protoconch/teleoconch transition, denoted by the change of sculpture but not clearly delimited; this protoconch has about 2.1 whorls. B. Measurement of apical angle for early whorls and for later whorls, using tangent lines. C. Descriptive terms, ad: adapical cord; m: median cord; ab: abapical cord; sp: subperipheral cord (in prolongation of the suture on last whorl, sometimes partly exposed above the suture on spire whorls); ba: basal cord; ha: height of aperture.

Figura 1. Convenciones utilizadas en las descripciones de las conchas. A. Vista apical mostrando las opciones tomadas para el recuento de vueltas y el recuento de costillas en una vuelta. N: núcleo; P/T: transición protoconcha/teleoconcha, denotada por el cambio de escultura pero no claramente delimitada; esta protoconcha tiene alrededor de 2,1 vueltas. B. Medición del ángulo apical para primeras y últimas vueltas, utilizando líneas tangentes. C. Términos descriptivos, ad: cordón adapical; m: cordón mediano; ab: cordón abapical; sp: cordón subperiférico (en prolongación de la sutura en la última vuelta, a veces parcialmente expuesto por encima de la sutura en la espira); ba: cordón basal; ha: altura de la abertura.

Frankfurt am Main. Other material from Seamount 2 is deposited in MNHN, whereas that from Meteor cruise is stored in the voucher collection at Senckenberg am Meer (SaM), Wilhelmshaven.

Shells were measured using an ocular micrometer under the stereomicroscope. Scanning electron micrographs were used for partial views of protoconchs and microsculptures. Measurements of height of aperture refer to the internal part (excluding thickness of shell). Protoconch whorls were counted as described by VERDUIN (1982), discounting the first half of the nucleus; whorl counts with this protocol are by

about half a whorl higher than as described in FERNANDES *ET AL.* (2015). Ribs per whorl were counted under the stereomicroscope, holding the shell in apical view. Apical angles were measured after tracing straight lines tangential to the whorls on printouts of the apertural views; this measurement is therefore independent of the thickness of the apical whorl (Figure 1).

Shells used for scanning electron microscopy were cleaned with a very brief immersion in an ultrasonic cleaner, usually after washing in a 10% solution of sodium-lauryl sulphate, a detergent. Selected shells were imaged using a

Nikon DXM camera attached to a Nikon SMZ1000 stereomicroscope or a JEOL JCC 1100 scanning electron microscope at University of Málaga, or using a Keyence digital microscope and a Vega3-Tescan scanning electron microscope at Senckenberg am Meer. Focus-stacking was performed with the CombineZM software (HADLEY, 2006).

Abbreviations:

Measurements.

H: height;

Ha: height of aperture (measured inside);

Hp: height of exposed protoconch;

W: width or maximum diameter;

Wp: width or maximum diameter of exposed protoconch.

Institutions.

MNHN: Muséum National de Histoire Naturelle, Paris;

SMF: Senckenberg Naturmuseum, Frankfurt am Main;

SaM: Senckenberg am Meer, Wilhelmshaven.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795

Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960

Superfamily TRIPHOROIDEA Gray, 1847

Family CERITHIOPSIDAE H. Adams & A. Adams, 1853

Genus *Cerithiopsis* Forbes & Hanley, 1850

Type species: *Cerithiopsis tubercularis* (Montagu, 1803), by monotypy.

Cerithiopsis cf. *fayalensis* Watson, 1880 (Fig. 2A-F)

Material examined (total 15 shells): AZORES • 4 shells (Fig. 2A-F); Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble • 2 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.661°N, 25.918°W; 599 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23112; grab in sand and coral rubble. ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 3 shells; 33.997°N, 30.177°W; 617 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23408; grab in bioclastic sand. TYRO SEAMOUNT • 3 shells; 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 29.568°N, 28.339°W; 855 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/23425-R9, ROV sample. LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 29.645°N, 28.975°W; 284 m; 27-Oct.2018; M151/GeoB23440; grab in bioclastic sand.

Type locality: off Fayal, Azores, 38.633°N, 28.475°W, 450-500 fms (823-914 m) ["Challenger" sta. 75].

Distribution: Azorean seamounts (Mar da Prata, Atlantis, Tyro, Great Meteor, Little Meteor Seamount), 284-890 m (our material). The typical *C. fayalensis* with a brown shell is known from the Azores (type locality; FRIAS MARTINS ET AL. 2009), Madeira (SEGERS ET AL., 2009), the Lusitanian seamounts, the Ibero-Moroccan area and throughout the Mediterranean Sea (GOFAS ET AL. 2011; MANOUSIS & GALINOU-MITSOU, 2014; ASLAN & OVALIS, 2017), where it is rare in 37-200 m depths.

Remarks: Specimens examined here most resemble *Cerithiopsis fayalensis*, but differ in the colour of the teleoconch, which is whitish instead of dark brown. *Cerithiopsis atalaya* Watson, 1885 is similar in profile and sculpture but has a completely different protoconch, with two strong spiral keels crossing the axial ribs (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993). The empty shells of *Cerithiopsis* cf. *fayalensis* have been found in bioclastic sand with remains of scleractinians, hydrozoans, echinoderms and foraminiferans.

Figure 2. A-F. *Cerithiopsis* cf. *fayalensis* Watson, 1880. A-C: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/GeoB23111 (H 4.4 mm) and protoconch; D: detail of the sculpture of the last whorl; E, F: same locality (H 3.2 mm), shell and protoconch. G-L. *Cerithiopsis slikeri* n. sp. G, H: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 834 m, M151/GeoB23109 (H 4.9 mm); I: protoconch; J: detail of the sculpture of the last whorl; K, L: holotype from Tyro Seamount, 890 m, SMT2/DW278 (H 4.7 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 2. A-F. *Cerithiopsis* cf. *fayalensis* Watson, 1880. A-C: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/GeoB23111 (H 4,4 mm) y protoconcha; D: detalle de la escultura de la última vuelta; E, F: misma localidad (H 3,2 mm), concha y protoconcha. G-L. *Cerithiopsis slikeri* n. sp. G, H: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, 834 m, M151/GeoB23109 (H 4,9 mm); I: protoconcha; J: detalle de la escultura de la última vuelta; K: holotipo del Banco Tyro, 890 m, SMT2/DW278 (H 4,7 mm) y protoconcha.

Cerithiopsis slikeri n. sp. (Fig. 2G-L)

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Type material. *Holotype*: TYRO SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 2K, L); 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38567. *Paratypes*: TYRO SEAMOUNT • 9 shells; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38568.

Other material examined (total 4 shells): AZORES • 1 shell (Fig. 2G-J); Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.926°W; 834 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23109; grab in coral rubble; SaM86306. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge. LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 29.654°N, 29.015°W; 852 m; 27 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23436; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM84399.

Type locality: Tyro Seamount, 33.963°N, 28.373°W, 890–925 m.

Etymology: *slikeri* honours Henk Sliker, honorary curator of Malacology in the Natural History Museum in Rotterdam, for creating the photo library that enabled global web accessibility of mollusc images.

Description (based on holotype): Shell small (H 4.7 mm, W 1.2 mm, Ha 0.50 mm [10% of total height]), with highly raised, regularly conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.45 mm, Wp 0.31 mm) multispiral with 3 ¼ whorls, highly raised, apical angle ca. 18°, in two stages; protoconch I with 1 ¼ whorls, inflated, well-rounded, with a rugged surface, diameter 0.21 mm; protoconch II convex with 2 regularly growing whorls, two spiral keels equidistant from sutures and from each other, and fine, slightly procline axial riblets narrower than their interspaces. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture and sharply delimited.

Teleoconch with 9 ¾ whorls, apical angle starting ca. 15°, then decreasing to ca. 10° in the last two whorls. Spire whorls strongly ornamented with spiral cords and axial ribs. Two strong spiral cords in the spire whorls, equidistant from sutures and from each other, and a faint swelling below the suture forming an indistinct adapical spiral cord. Nearly orthocone axial ribs, 13–17 per whorl, forming beads at intersections with cords. Numerous fine growth lines.

Last whorl with a smooth subperipheral cord, delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture trapezoidal, with a twisted siphonal canal. Columella straight, at a blunt angle with parietal side. Columellar and parietal callus marked but thin. Outer lip orthocone,

slightly convex, internally smooth with imprint of external sculpture.

Protoconch pale brown, teleoconch whitish, with columella stained faintly pale brown.

Variability: The largest shell is 6.5 mm high with broken early whorls (estimated 7.5 mm when complete). Colour pattern is quite uniform.

Distribution: Azorean Seamounts (Mar da Prata; Tyro, Plato and Little Meteor seamounts), 690–852 m (our material). The shell figured in HOFFMAN, VAN HEUGTEN & LAVALEYE (2011: 42, fig. 4) could be this species, which extends the distribution to the Rockall Bank, 587 m.

Remarks: *Cerithiopsis slikeri* n. sp. shares with *Cerithiopsis atalaya* Watson, 1885, the unusual morphology of the protoconch, with two strong spiral keels crossing the axial ribs-. The latter was originally described from Madeira and later reported from several localities in the East Atlantic and Mediterranean (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993; HERNÁNDEZ ET AL., 2011; GOFAS ET AL., 2011; MANOUSIS & GALINOU-MITSOU, 2014; ROMANI ET AL., 2020). However, the lectotype of *C. atalaya* (available from <<https://gbmolluscatypes.ac.uk>>) and other specimens examined from the Alboran Sea have three spiral cords with distinct beads at the intersections with the ribs, the last whorl having the adapical (subsutural) cord as strong as the median cord or even stronger. The teleoconch of *C. atalaya* also differs in colour, being dark brown instead of whitish.

Figure 3. A, B. *Cerithiopsis minima* (Brusina, 1865), shell from Little Meteor Seamount, 284 m, M151/GeoB23440 (H 2.8 mm). C-E. *Cerithiopsis diadema* Monterosato, 1874, shell from the Azores, Açor Seamount, 339 m, M151/GeoB23139 (H 2.9 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 3. A, B. *Cerithiopsis minima* (Brusina, 1865), concha del Pequeño Banco Meteor, 284 m, M151/GeoB23440 (H 2,8 mm). C-E. *Cerithiopsis diadema* Monterosato, 1874, concha de las Azores, Banco Açor, 339 m, M151/GeoB23139 (H 2,9 mm) y protoconcha.

Cerithiopsis minima (Brusina, 1865) (Fig. 3A, B)

Material examined (4 shells): GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 29.750°N, 28.466°W; 291 m; 21 Mar. 2010; POS397-111-1; Shipek grab in bioclastic sand • 1 shell; 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge. LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 3A, B); 29.645°N, 28.975°W; 284 m; 27-Oct.2018; M151/GeoB23440; grab in bioclastic sand.

Distribution: Western Europe from the Basque coast to Morocco, and the entire Mediterranean Sea (GOFAS *ET AL.*, 2011). The species has also been reported in Madeira (SEGERS *ET AL.*, 2009) and the Azores (FRIAS MARTINS *ET AL.*, 2009).

Remarks: DAUTZENBERG (1889) and FRIAS MARTINS *ET AL.* (2009) reported *Cerithiopsis tubercularis* (Montagu, 1803), *Cerithiopsis minima* and other shallow water species from the infralittoral zone of the Azores, but only these worn shells of *C. minima* were found in our material.

Cerithiopsis diadema Monterosato, 1874 (Fig. 3C-E)

Material examined (5 shells): AZORES • 2 shells (Fig. 3C-E); Açor Seamount; 38.156°N, 29.084°W; 339 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/23139; grab in coral rubble; SaM85839 • 3 shells; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.675°N, 25.717°W; 311 m; 16 Oct. 2018; M151/23161; grab in live coral with rubble; SaM85082.

Distribution: Western Europe from the Basque coast to tropical West Africa, and the entire Mediterranean (GOFAS *ET AL.* 2011); also in the Canaries (HERNÁNDEZ *ET AL.* 2011), Madeira (SEGERS *ET AL.* 2009) and the Azores (our material, it seems to be the first record).

Remarks: These are much worn shells (probably derived from post-mortem dislodgement) but conserve remains of the very characteristic protoconch of this species, featuring a distinct keel close to the abapical suture and fine axial ribs.

Genus *Krachia* Baluk, 1975

Type species: *Cerithiopsis korytnicensis* Baluk, 1975, by original designation.

The presence of two thin spiral keels surrounding a flat base is an uncommon character state in Cerithiopsidae, and within the European fauna is restricted to *Krachia* spp. and to *Cerithiopsis diadema*. The latter has a very different, unmistakable protoconch (Fig. 3C, see also GOFAS ET AL. 2011: 159). Species of *Krachia* are diagnosed by having a protoconch of 2-3 whorls with a smooth initial whorl, usually with continuous, flexuous axial ribs or folds on the last protoconch whorl, and the paired cords around the base of the teleoconch.

Three deep-water species of *Krachia* were reported from the mid-Atlantic by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993): *Krachia cossmanni* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), *K. guernei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) and *K. obeliscoides* (Jeffreys, 1885). *Krachia cossmanni* was not represented in our material and stands out for its multispir-

al protoconch of two and a half smooth whorls, more inflated than the first teleoconch whorl (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993, fig. 1356, not figs 1344-1345, see below remarks under *Cerithiella metula*).

Two shallow-water species of *Krachia* are reported from the Eastern Atlantic: *K. tiara* (Monterosato, 1874) and *K. cylindrata* (Jeffreys, 1885). The former was originally described from Madeira and it extends into the Mediterranean (ÖZTÜRK ET AL., 2008; MANOUSIS ET AL., 2018); it has a dark brown shell with two successive ribbed whorls on the protoconch (lectotype illustrated by APPOLLONI ET AL. 2018, and another specimen from Madeira by SEGERS ET AL. 2009). *Krachia cylindrata*, described from the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and the Mediterranean, has a pale tawny shell and a minute, more conical protoconch with only one ribbed whorl (illustrated in GOFAS ET AL. 2011).

Krachia guernei (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 4A-C)

Material examined: HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 4B, C); 31.076°N, 28.815°W; 1660–1735 m; 19 Jan.1993; SMT2/DW204; dredge.

Type locality: off Azores, 37.711°N, 25.087°W, 1385 m (Monaco sta. 553).

Distribution: The species is known from upper bathyal zones South of the eastern Azores (type locality) and the Hyères Seamount (this study), depth range 1385–1735 m.

Remarks: There was only one shell in our material that could be assigned to this species, and it originated from one of the deepest samples. The low apical angle (ca. 18° at the beginning of the spire, reducing to 10–12° at the last whorls) and the narrow opisthocline

ribs, more conspicuous than the spiral sculpture, and the presence of only two spiral cords, are characteristic of this species. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993: 606) selected the originally figured shell as lectotype (stored in Monaco Oceanographic Museum, MOM). We believe that the shell represented in BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993: fig. 1349), which has a notably wider apical angle and a more distinctly ribbed protoconch, belongs to a different species.

Krachia cf. *obeliscoides* (Jeffreys, 1885) (Fig. 4D-F)

Material examined (total 10 shells): HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 31.314°N, 28.559°W; 1370–1480 m; 18 Jan.1993; SMT2/DW197 • 8 shells (Fig. 4D-F); 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan.1993; SMT2/DW203; dredge • 1 shell; 31.076°N, 28.815°W; 1660–1735 m; 19 Jan.1993; SMT2/DW204; dredge.

Figure 4. A-C. *Krachia guernei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A: lectotype from the Azores, 1385 m, Monaco sta. 553 (H 4.5 mm; reproduced from DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896); B, C: shell from Hyères Seamount, 1660-1735 m, SMT2/DW204 (H 5.1 mm) and protoconch. D-F. *Krachia cf. obeliscoides* (Jeffreys, 1885). D, E: shell from Hyères Seamount, 845 m, SMT2/DW203 (H 3.6 mm) and protoconch; F: shell from the same locality (H 5.7 mm).

Figura 4. A-C. *Krachia guernei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A: lectotipo de las Azores, 1385 m, Mónaco sta. 553 (H 4,5 mm; reproducido de DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896); B, C: concha del Banco Hyères, 1735 m, SMT2/DW204 (H 5,1 mm) y protoconcha. D-F. *Krachia cf. obeliscoides* (Jeffreys, 1885). D, E: concha del Banco Hyères, 845 m, SMT2/DW203 (H 3,6 mm) y protoconcha; F: concha de la misma localidad (H 5,7 mm).

Type locality: Off Portugal, 39.650° to 39.916°N, 09.650° to 09.933°W, 1092–1993 m [Porcupine 1870 sta. 16, 17, 17a].

Distribution: Off Portugal (type locality), NW Morocco, the Azores (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993) and Hyères Seamount (our material). Known depth range is 845–2165 m.

Remarks: *Krachia obeliscoides* was described with 3–6 spiral cords (JEFFREYS 1885: 55, pl. 6 fig. 4) and with a finer reticulated sculpture than *K. cossmanni* (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993: figs

1346, 1348; figuring a syntype with a concave outline, 4–5 spiral cords and dense oblique axial ribs). Our material is conspecific with the shell from the Azores figured by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993: fig. 1347) but there are differences with the syntype from western Portugal. The protoconch has a smooth initial whorl and axial ribs on the second whorl.

Krachia cochleapex n. sp. (Fig. 5A-E)

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Type material. *Holotype*: PLATO SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 5A-C); 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge, in sediment with dead coral fragments; MNHN-IM-2000-38569. *Paratypes*: PLATO SEAMOUNT • 10 shells (Fig. 5D, E); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38570.

Other material examined (total 76 shells): ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 4 shells identified as *Krachia* cf. *cochleapex* (Fig. 5F-H); 34.373°N, 30.463°W; 1190–1340 m; 03 Feb. 1993, SMT2/DW261; dredge. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 36 shells (mostly worn); 33.220°N, 29.137°W; 1360–1420 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW243; dredge • 30 shells; 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 4 shells identified as *Krachia* cf. *cochleapex* (Fig. 5I, J); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW200; dredge • 2 shells identified as *Krachia* cf. *cochleapex*; 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW203; dredge.

Type locality: Plato Seamount, 33.210°N, 29.287°W, 1450–1500 m.

Etymology: the name, formed from Latin *cochlea*, a coiled shell, and *apex*, alludes to the twisted and drawn out shape of the apical whorls.

Description (based on holotype): Shell small (H 4.9 mm, W 1.8 mm, Ha 1.05 mm [21% of total height]), with a raised, regularly conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.52 mm, Wp 0.47 mm) composed of 1.5 whorl. First whorl pointed and distinctly drawn out, smooth, diameter 0.1 mm; following whorl with rather straight axial ribs and smooth interspaces. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not clearly demarcated.

Teleoconch with 6.5 whorls regularly increasing in diameter, apical angle 22° decreasing to 20°, spire whorls strongly ornamented with spiral cords, thinner than the interspaces, and axial ribs. Two spiral cords (median and abapical) on the first two teleoconch whorls, the median one more distant from the suture than from the abapical cord; a third (adapical) spiral cord emerges on the third whorl and remains more distant from the suture than from the median cord. Orthocline to prosocline axial ribs, 20–21 per whorl, somewhat narrower than interspaces, forming beads at intersections and thinner between spiral cords. Surface with numerous fine growth lines.

Last whorl with two additional spirals, smooth and thin, a subperipheral cord and a basal cord very close to it and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture subquadrangular. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocline, internally smooth with imprint of external sculpture. Siphonal canal prominent, slightly

twisted laterally and backwards, broadly open.

Colour entirely white.

Variability: All the shells from Plato Seamount have, like the holotype, a prominently drawn out apex of the protoconch, tapering to a small nucleus pointing at 45° with respect to the axis of coiling. All shells from Atlantis Seamount have this feature much less pronounced (Fig. 5F-H), and the nucleus is hardly protruding on shells from Hyères Seamount (Fig. 5I, J) which also has only two spiral cords. The general build is otherwise similar and suggest that they are the same species with some differentiation between seamounts. The orientation of the axial ribs may vary from prosocline to nearly orthocline on different whorls of the same shell. The largest shell (a paratype from SMT2/DW250) measures 8.3 x 2.5 mm without the protoconch.

Distribution: Plato Seamount (type locality), Atlantis and Hyères seamounts (*Krachia* cf. *cochleapex*).

Remarks: *Krachia cochleapex* has a considerably broader apical angle (22° even on last whorls) than *Krachia guernei* (Fig. 4A-C; 18° at the start of teleoconch, reducing to 10° on last whorls), but the most remarkable difference is in the protoconch. The prevalence of the oblique axial sculpture over the spiral cords distinguishes these two species from other *Krachia* spp. found on the upper part of the South Azorean seamounts. The protruding siphonal canal is a conspicuous character, shared with *Krachia* cf. *obeliscoides*.

Figure 5. A-E. *Krachia cochleapex* n. sp. A-C: holotype from Plato Seamount, 1450–1500 m, SMT2/DW250 (H 4.9 mm), and protoconch; D, E: paratype from the same locality (H 4.4 mm), and protoconch. F-J. *Krachia* cf. *cochleapex* n. sp. F-H: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 1190–1340 m, SMT2/DW 261 (H 5.0 mm), and protoconch; I, J: shell from Hyères Seamount, 1060 m, SMT2/DW200 (H 3.9 mm), and protoconch.

Figura 5. A-E. *Krachia cochleapex* n. sp. A-C: holotipo del Banco Plato, 1450–1500 m, SMT2/DW250 (H 4,9 mm) y protoconcha; D, E: paratipo de la misma localidad (H 4,4 mm) y protoconcha. F-I. *Krachia* cf. *cochleapex* n. sp. F-H: concha del Banco Atlantis, 1190–1340 m, SMT2/DW 261 (H 5,0 mm) y protoconcha; I, J: concha del Banco Hyères, 1060 m, SMT2/DW200 (H 3,9 mm) y protoconcha.

Krachia trauseli n. sp. (Fig. 6A-K)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:3419A0D2-6CB9-4F4F-95CC-43EC177EC0AD

Type material (total 33 shells). *Holotype*: AZORES • 1 shell (Fig. 6A-D); José Gaspar Seamount; 37.675°N, 25.717°W; 337 m; 06 Oct. 2018; M151/23105-2; grab in coral rubble; MNHN-IM-2000-38571. *Paratypes*: AZORES • 2 shells; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38589 • 1 shell (Fig.

6E-G); same data as for holotype; SMF 359011 • 1 shell; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.672°N, 25.713°W; 533 m; 18 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23172; grab; SaM 87183 • 2 shells; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.659°N, 25.788°W; 600 m; 18 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23173; grab; SaM 87185 • 1 shell; Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.926°W; 834 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23109; grab, coral rubble; SMF 359012 • 18 shells (Fig. 6H-K); Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble; SMF 359013 • 5 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.661°N, 25.918°W; 599 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23112; grab in sand and coral rubble; SaM 86304 • 2 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.906°W; 406 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23114; grab, sand and coral rubble; SaM 87186.

Other material examined: AZORES • 4 shells; Açor Seamount; 38.1557°N, 29.0840°W; 339 m; 14 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23139; grab in coral rubble; SaM 85840.

Type locality: Azores, José Gaspar Seamount, 37.675°N, 25.717°W, 337 m.

Etymology: *trauseli* honours Joop Trausel, honorary curator of Malacology in the Natural History Museum in Rotterdam, for donating his high-quality collection to the museum and making it digitally accessible.

Description (based on holotype): Shell small (H 3.3 mm, W 1.0 mm, Ha 0.48 mm [15% of total height]), with a raised conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.39 mm, Wp 0.34 mm) highly raised, apical angle about 30°, of nearly three whorls. Nucleus rounded, smooth, diameter 0.16 mm; following whorls with smooth and flexuous, oblique axial ribs, and smooth interspaces, initial ribs finer, closely set. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not clearly demarcated.

Teleoconch with 7 whorls regularly increasing in diameter, apical angle about 25° on early whorls, reducing to 17° on last whorls, spire whorls strongly ornamented with spiral cords and axial ribs. Three spiral cords on the spire whorls; subsutural (adapical) cord weakest, becoming about half as thick as the other two on last whorl, median and abapical spirals strong, about as thick as interspaces, the median one equidistant to suture and to abapical cord, the latter somewhat closer to suture. Orthocone axial ribs, 11-17 per whorl, somewhat narrower than interspaces, forming thick beads at intersections and thinner between spiral cords. Surface with numerous fine growth lines.

Last whorl with two additional thin spirals, a subperipheral cord and a basal cord very close to it and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture subquadrangular. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocone, internally smooth. Siphonal canal short, twisted laterally and backwards.

Colour of protoconch slightly pale brown; teleoconch opaque white with one brown spiral band below the suture and another spiral band, paler, at the periphery of last whorl (sometimes visible just above the suture of earlier whorls).

Variability: Among the shells from the Azores with coloured bands as in the holotype, the protoconch is highly variable (Hp 0.36–0.42 mm, Wp 0.33–0.35 mm with 2.5 to nearly 3 whorls). The number, extension and strength of axial ribs also varies considerably: strong, widely spaced ribs starting immediately after the nucleus (as in the holotype) or fine, closely packed ribs limited to the second protoconch whorl on the illustrated paratypes.

The teleoconch displays little variability in sculpture but the adapical (subsutural) cord may be inconspicuous, particularly on the early whorls. The number of axial ribs varies between whorls. Maximum size from worn shells is about 5 mm.

Distribution: Azores (São Miguel) (FRIAS MARTINS *ET AL.*, 2009) and Azorean seamounts (Mar da Prata, José Gaspar Seamount, Açor Seamount), 234–834 m.

Remarks: *Krachia trauseli* n. sp. is the only NE Atlantic bathyal species in Cerithiopsidae with a brown spiral band. The presence of colour banding seems a species-specific character in that family, also known in *Cerithiopsis pulvis* (Issel, 1869), a shallow-water species introduced from the Indo-Pacific to the Mediterranean Sea, and in many coastal species of the Caribbean (ROLÁN *ET AL.*,

Figure 6. *Krachia trauseli* n. sp., Azores. A-C: holotype, José Gaspar Seamount, 329 m, M151/GeoB23105 (H 3.3 mm), and protoconch; D: detail of the sculpture of the last whorl; E-G: paratype 1, same locality (H 2.3 mm), and protoconch; H-J: paratype 2, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/GeoB23111 (H 3.2 mm), and protoconch; K: detail of the sculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 6. Krachia trauseli n. sp., Azores. A-C: *holotipo*, Banco José Gaspar, 329 m, M151/GeoB23105 (H 3,3 mm) y protoconcha; D: *detalle de la escultura de la última vuelta*; E-G: *paratipo 1*, misma localidad (H 2,3 mm) y protoconcha; H-J: *paratipo 2*, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/GeoB23111 (H 3,2 mm) y protoconcha; K: *detalle de la escultura de la última vuelta*.

2007). FRIAS MARTINS *ET AL.* (2009, fig. 81) illustrated a shell of this species, with a protoconch similar to that of the holotype, from off Vila Franca do Campo, São Miguel, Azores (approx. 37°42'N, 25°24'W, 117-234 m), identified as *Krachia* cf. *guernei* (Dautzenberg &

Fischer, 1896). The Madeiran *Krachia tiara* (Monterosato, 1874) has a protoconch quite similar to the holotype of *K. trauseli* but differs not only in being uniformly dark brown in colour but also in having thicker, more rounded beads at the intersections.

Two very similar, but entirely white forms resembling *K. trauseli* are found further south on Great Meteor Seamount. One of them, described hereafter as *Krachia meteoris* n. sp., differs in

having a narrower apical angle, and a sculpture in which the spirals, where overrunning the ribs, form flattened projections rather than rounded beads as in other species of the genus.

Krachia stilapex n. sp. (Fig. 7B-M)

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Type material. *Holotype*: ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 7B-E); 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38572. *Paratypes*: • 2 shells; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38573.

Other material examined (total 30 shells): ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 8 shells (worn; Fig. 7F); 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW263; dredge. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 7G, H); 32.264°N, 27.531°W; 670–715 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW237; dredge. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 4 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge • 1 shell; 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge, in sediment with dead coral fragments. TYRO SEAMOUNT • 6 shells; 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 6 shells (Fig. 7I-K); 31.387°N, 28.892°W; 480 m; 15 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW182; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 3 shells (Fig. 7L, M); 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, 33.997°N, 30.203°W, 420–460 m.

Etymology: the name alludes to the turreted, narrow protoconch.

Description (based on the juvenile holotype): Shell small (H 2.4 mm, W 1.0 mm, Ha 0.5 mm [20% of total height]), with a raised conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.53 mm, Wp 0.45 mm) highly elevated, apical angle about 25°, multispiral of nearly three whorls. Nucleus rounded, smooth, diameter 0.18 mm; following whorls convex, rather smooth, bearing very tenuous, irregular spiral threads, most visible on the abapical part of the second whorl, and growth lines becoming conspicuous and flexuous on the last whorl. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not clearly demarcated.

Teleoconch with 4 whorls regularly increasing in diameter, apical angle about 26° on early whorls, reducing to 19° on last whorls, spire whorls strongly ornamented with spiral cords and axial ribs. Three spiral cords on the spire whorls; subsutural (adapical) spiral cord weakest, becoming about half as thick as the other two on last whorl, median and abapical spirals strong, as thick as interspaces, the median one equidistant to suture and to abapical cord, which is somewhat closer to the suture. Orthocline axial ribs, 16–17 per whorl, somewhat narrower than interspaces, forming thick beads at intersections and

(Right page) Figure 7. A. *Krachia cossmanni* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), lectotype (H 8.3 mm) from the Azores, 1385 m, Monaco sta. 553 (H 8.3 mm; reproduced from DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896). B-M. *Krachia stilapex* n. sp. B-D: holotype from Atlantis Seamount, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 2.4 mm), and protoconch; E: detail of protoconch microsculpture; F: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 5.7 mm); G, H: shell from Irving Seamount, 670 m, SMT2/DW237 (H 2.5 mm), and protoconch; I, J: shell from Hyères Seamount, 480 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 3.5 mm), and protoconch; K: protoconch of another shell, same locality, arrow points to protoconch-teleoconch limit; L, M: shell from Great Meteor Seamount, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 3.8 mm), and protoconch.

Figura 7. A. *Krachia cossmanni* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), lectotipo (H 8,3 mm) de las Azores, 1385 m, Mónaco sta. 553 (H 8,3 mm; reproducido de DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896). B-M. *Krachia stilapex* n. sp. B-D: holotipo del Banco Atlantis, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 2,4 mm) y protoconcha; E: detalle de microescultura de la protoconcha; F: concha del Banco Atlantis, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 5,7 mm); G, H: concha del Banco Irving, 670 m, SMT2/DW237 (H 2,5 mm) y protoconcha; I, J: concha del Banco Hyères, 480 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 3,5 mm) y protoconcha; K: protoconcha de otra concha, misma localidad, la flecha apunta al límite protoconcha-teleoconcha; L, M: concha del Gran Banco Meteor, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 3,8 mm) y protoconcha.

thinner between spiral cords. Surface with numerous fine growth lines.

Last whorl with two additional spirals, a subperipheral cord and a basal cord very close to it and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture subquadrangular; concave parietal area and upper columella delimiting siphonal canal. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocline, internally smooth. Siphonal canal short, twisted laterally and backwards.

Colour entirely white.

Variability: The holotype is juvenile and was selected for having a well-preserved protoconch; the largest shell was found on Atlantis Seamount and measures 5.7 mm high, with measurements of the protoconch similar to the holotype, and has eight teleoconch whorls and the aperture 0.90 mm (16% of total height). Apical angle is 22-26° on early teleoconch whorls, reducing to 15-20° on later whorls. The single shell found on Irving Seamount is small (2.5 mm), its protoconch has hardly 2.5 whorls and the subsutural cord is inconspicuous.

Distribution: Azorean seamounts, 30–34°N, 28–31°W, 420–890 m

Remarks: *Krachia stilapex* n. sp. differs from *K. cossmanni* (Fig. 7A: lectotype designated by BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993) in

having a protoconch markedly narrower than the first teleoconch whorl (with three swollen whorls, but surpassing in thickness the first teleoconch whorl in *K. cossmanni*). It is also much smaller (largest shell 5.7 mm vs. 8.3 mm, both with 9 teleoconch whorls). *Krachia guernei* differs in having the axial ribs more distinctly prevalent over the spiral sculpture, whereas *K. stilapex* has the main spiral cords more conspicuous than the axial ribs, assuming the aspect of beaded spiral keels on some specimens. The protoconch of *K. stilapex* n. sp. is also narrower than that of *K. guernei* (Wp 0.45 mm vs. 0.56 mm in our shell of *K. guernei*), lacks axial ribs and is conical rather than pupoid. Both *K. trauseli* n. sp. and *K. meteoris* n. sp. differ in having a protoconch which is broader, less turreted, and distinctly ribbed. The faint, irregular spiral microsculpture observed on the protoconch of *K. stilapex* n. sp. is so far unique in this genus.

The interpretation of the protoconch is not straightforward in this species; the curvature of the growth lines near the transition to the teleoconch are reminiscent of the sinuses which accommodate the velum in planktotrophic larvae, but such curvature is also seen in non-swimming larvae.

Krachia meteoris n. sp. (Fig. 8A-F)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7D16A170-7D7C-470B-A91D-3F04FE5E050A

Type material (total 11 shells). **Holotype:** GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 8 A-B); 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38587. **Paratypes:** GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 10 shells (Fig. 8C-F); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38588.

Other material examined: PLATO SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 33.205°N, 29.032°W; 565 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW240; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell identified as *Krachia* cf. *meteoris*; 31.387°N, 28.892°W; 480 m; 15 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW182; dredge.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, 30.033°N, 28.368°W, 470 m.

Etymology: the name alludes to the Great Meteor Seamount, where the species was found.

Description (based on holotype): Shell small (H 3.5 mm, W 1.2 mm, Ha 0.65 mm [18% of total height]), with a raised conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.45 mm, Wp 0.45 mm) raised, apical angle about 30°, of ca. 2.5 whorls, with a shallow, impressed

suture. Nucleus and first whorl rounded, smooth, diameter 0.18 mm; following whorl convex, rather smooth, bearing fine, slightly opisthocline ribs narrower than their interspaces. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not clearly demarcated.

Figure 8. A-F. *Krachia meteoris* n. sp. Great Meteor Seamount, 470 m, SMT2/DW152. A, B: holotype (H 3.5 mm) and protoconch; C, D: paratype (H 3.6 mm) and protoconch; E, F: paratype (H 4.0 mm) and protoconch. G, H. *Krachia* sp. 1., shell from Great Meteor Seamount, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 2.5 mm) and protoconch. I, J. *Krachia* sp. 2., shell from Great Meteor Seamount, 855 m, M151/GeoB23425R9 (H 2.9 mm) and protoconch.

Figura 8. A-F Krachia meteoris n. sp., Gran Banco Meteor, 470 m, SMT2/DW152. A, B: holotipo (H 3,5 mm) y protoconcha; C, D: paratipo (H 3,6 mm) y protoconcha; E-F: paratipo (H 4,0 mm) y protoconcha. G, H. *Krachia* sp. 1., concha del Gran Banco Meteor, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 2,5 mm), y protoconcha. I, J. *Krachia* sp. 2., concha del Gran Banco Meteor, 855 m, M151/GeoB23425R9 (H 2,9 mm), y protoconcha.

Teleoconch with 6.5 whorls regularly increasing in diameter, apical angle 23° on first whorls, reducing to 12° on last whorls, spire whorls strongly ornamented with spiral cords and axial ribs. Three spiral cords on the spire whorls; subsutural (adapical) spiral cord

weakest, very narrow and appressed to the suture, median and abapical spirals narrower than interspaces, equidistant to sutures and to each other. Opisthocline axial ribs, 18-20 on last whorls, somewhat narrower than interspaces, overrun by the spiral cords, which do not form defi-

nite beads at the intersections. Surface with numerous fine growth lines.

Last whorl with two additional spirals, a subperipheral cord and a basal cord very close to it and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture rhomboidal. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocline, internally smooth. Siphonal canal short, straight. Columellar and parietal callus narrow, marked but thin.

Colour entirely white.

Variability: Little variability was observed among the few shells available. A single shell from Hyères Seamount differs in having a very inflated first whorl of the protoconch. The largest shell is 4.6 x 1.5 mm.

Remarks: This species is similar to *Krachia trauseli* n. sp. except for the colour which is always white, and it also differs

in having a smaller apical angle and oblique, opisthocline axial ribs. There is one teleoconch whorl less at the same size and the spiral cords are narrower, not forming beads (but only elevations) at their intersection with the ribs. *Krachia guernei* is also similar regarding the apical angle and rib morphology, but does not show so definite ribs on the protoconch, axial ribs more prevalent over the spiral sculpture and has a more protruding siphonal canal. Besides those differences with *K. trauseli* n. sp., the consideration of distinct species is supported by the fact that, despite a thorough sampling shallower than 500 m, all *Krachia* found on Atlantis and Irving seamounts have the smooth, pointed protoconch characteristic of *K. stilapex* n. sp. Nonetheless, the protoconch of *K. meteoris* n. sp. resembles that of some specimens of *K. trauseli* (Figs. 6G, J).

Krachia sp. 1 (Fig. 8G, H)

Material examined: GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 2 shells (Fig. 8G, H); 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge.

Remarks: This morph differs from *Krachia meteoris* n. sp. by the protoconch, which has a smaller, more protruding and very convex first whorl, and very

fine ribs only on the last part. The axial ribs are orthocline and the apical angle is higher like in *K. trauseli*. Only two shells were found.

Krachia sp. 2 (Figs. 8I, J)

Material examined: GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 8I, J); 29.568°N, 28.340°W; 855 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23425R9; ROV grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble.

Remarks: This is a small form with coarse mesh formed by narrow ribs and

cords, probably a different species, but only one shell was found.

Genus *Onchodia* Dall, 1924

Type species: *Laskeya benthica* Dall, 1924, by original designation.

Onchodia tenuicula n. sp. (Fig. 9A-N)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7D5B262E-EE13-465F-A465-0F2E8F738490

Type material. *Holotype:* GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 9J, K); 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38574. *Paratypes:* GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 19 shells (Fig. 9L-N); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38575.

Other material examined (total 147 shells): AZORES • 1 shell; Açor Seamount; 38.359°N, 29.051°W; 648 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23135; grab in bioclastic sand • 24 shells (Fig. 9C-E); Açor Seamount; 38.156°N, 29.064°W; 339 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23139; grab in coral rubble • 4 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.926°W; 834 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23109; grab in coral rubble • 9 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble; grab • 17 shells (Fig. 9A, B); Mar da Prata; 37.661°N, 25.918°W; 599 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23112; grab in sand and coral rubble • 4 shells; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.675°N, 25.717°W; 329 m; 06-Oct.-2018; M151/GeoB23105-2; grab in coral rubble. ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 34.082°N, 30.255°W; 335–340 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW255; dredge • 1 shell (Fig. 9F, G); 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge • 8 shells (3.5 x 1.1 to 3.9 x 1.4 mm); 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW263; dredge • 3 shells; 33.971°N, 30.206°W; 677 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23404; grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble • 1 shell; 33.997°N, 30.177°W; 617 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23408; grab in bioclastic sand. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 32.264°N, 27.531°W; 670–715 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW237; dredge. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 4 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 47 shells (2.2 x 0.9 to 3.4 x 1.2 mm; Fig. 9H, I); 31.387°N, 28.892°W; 480 m; 15 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW182; dredge • 12 shells (3.4 x 1.3 to 4.0 x 1.6 mm); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW200; dredge • 1 shell (4.6 x 1.5 mm); 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW203; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (4.9 x 1.5 mm); 29.601°N, 28.380°W; 550–575 m; 13 Jan. 1994; SMT2/DW166; dredge • 1 shell; 29.565°N, 28.339°W; 944 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23425R6; ROV grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble • 3 shells; 29.568°N, 28.340°W; 855 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23425R9; ROV grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble. LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 3 shells; 29.655°N, 29.004°W; 464 m; 27 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23438; grab.

Type locality: Great Meteor Seamount, 30.033°N, 28.368°W, 470 m.

Etymology: the name means “skinny” and refers to the more delicate profile compared to the sturdy European *Onchodia valeriae* (Giusti, 1987).

Description (based on the holotype): Shell small (H 3.3 mm, W 1.1 mm, Ha 0.60 mm [18 % of total height]), with a raised conical, slightly cyrtoconoidal spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.38 mm, Wp 0.33 mm) with slightly more than 2 whorls, the first one smooth, the remainder with a sculpture of well delimited, raised flexuous axial riblets, half as wide as their interspaces, and of two very thin spiral cords of similar aspect, running along mid-whorl and hardly forming knobs at intersections with the ribs. Transition from smooth to ribbed part of the protoconch, and from protoconch to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not delimited by a definite line.

Teleoconch with 7 whorls, apical angle about 25° at the beginning of teleoconch, reducing to 10° in last whorls. Strong sculpture of spiral cords and axial ribs. First teleoconch whorl with a strong abapical spiral cord situated at the lower third, forming a keel, and an adapical one, rather indistinct; adapical cord more prominent on later

whorls but always lesser than the abapical one, and split in two weaker cords before reaching the outer lip. Orthocline axial ribs as broad as their interspaces, forming prominent knobs at intersection with cords and attenuated in the interspace between cords. Numerous fine growth lines. Last whorl with subperipheral and basal spiral cords, broader than their interspaces, devoid of knobs albeit somewhat wrinkled, the basal one smaller. Basal area convex.

Aperture with a slightly curved columella at a blunt angle with parietal side. Outer lip at an angle with parietal side, flaring, smooth inside, not indented by the termination of spiral cords. Siphonal canal short and nearly closed. Columellar callus forming a thin, appressed rim; parietal callus indistinct.

Colour entirely white.

Variability: Shell size from Meteor Bank is in the range 2.4 x 0.9 mm to 4.6 x 1.4 mm. The ribbed part of the protoconch may be up to 1.5 whorls in few specimens, and sometimes shows only one very thin spiral cordlet. Axial ribs

are much attenuated on one shell from Meteor (Fig. 9N), with knobs accordingly less marked on the major cord, which assumes a keeled aspect. Shells from deeper water tend to be larger.

Distribution: Azorean seamounts, 29–39°N, 25–31°W, 329–1060 m.

Remarks: *Onchodia valeriae* (Giusti, 1987), originally described from the Alboran sea and later also found in the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, is similar in shell height but distinctly broader; the beads are more definite, particularly on the adapical cord, the profile of the last whorl is well-rounded, not keeled along the abapical cord, and there are three (one subperipheral and two basal) beadless cords on the base (two in *O. tenuicula*). *Onchodia benthica* (Dall, 1924), the American type species, is larger (holotype 5.5 x 1.8 mm), has more bulging, bead-like knobs at the intersections of cords and

ribs, with not so much difference between adapical and abapical cords; there are also two (subperipheral and basal) cords but those are thinner, closer together and distant from the siphonal canal; the protoconch is more twisted and has sculpture only on its latest part. FERNANDES & PIMENTA (2017: fig. 1m) figured the holotype of *Onchodia benthica* and an alleged syntype of *Cerithiopsis georgiana* Dall, 1927 (fig. 1n), which is also *O. benthica* and is so discrepant with the original description of *C. georgiana* (described as having 14 teleoconch whorls) that it is certainly a mislabelled specimen. More generally, there is a need for a revision of Dall's types with careful comparisons with the original descriptions. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993: 612) reported that most of the Western Atlantic species described by DALL (1927) in *Onchodia* do not belong there.

Genus *Ekonos* Bouchet & Warén, 1993

Type species: *Cerithiella turbonilloides* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896, by original designation.

Ekonos turbonilloides (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 10A-E)

Material examined (total 15 shells): AZORES • 1 shell (Fig. 10A-C); Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.926°W; 834 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23109; grab, coral rubble; SaM86307. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 14 shells (Fig. 10D, E); 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge.

Type locality: off Azores, 38°33' N, 28°09' W, 1300 m.

Remarks: Only one shell from the Azores could be assigned to this species,

which was also found on Plato in the South Azorean seamounts.

Family NEWTONIELLIDAE Korobkov, 1955

Genus *Cerithiella* Verrill, 1882

Type species: *Cerithium metula* Lovén, 1846, by typification of replaced name *Lovenella* G.O. Sars, 1878.

Cerithiella candela Fernandes, Garofalo & Pimenta, 2015 (Fig. 10F, G)

Material examined (total 7 shells): HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 31.425°N, 28.864°W; 950–1250 m; 16 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW185; dredge • 1 shell; 31.436°N, 28.863°W; 1520 m; 16 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW186; dredge • 1 shell; 31.284°N, 28.489°W; 1780–1840 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW195; dredge • 1 shell; 31.313°N, 28.559°W; 1370–1480 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW197; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 3 shells (Fig. 10F, G); 30.068°N, 28.751°W; 1575–1610 m; 15 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW180.

Type locality: SW Brazil, Campos Basin, 21.894°S, 39.839°W, 1129 m.

Figure 9. *Onchodia tenuicula* n. sp. A, B: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 599 m, M151/GeoB23112 (H 3.5 mm), and protoconch; C, D: shell from Açor Seamount, 339 m, M151/GeoB23139 (H 3.1 mm), and protoconch; E, same locality, protoconch of another shell; F, G: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 2.7 mm), and protoconch; H, I: shell from Hyères Seamount, 480 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 3.4 mm), and protoconch; J, K: holotype from Great Meteor Seamount, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 3.3 mm), and protoconch; L, M: paratype, same locality (H 3.4 mm), and protoconch; N: paratype, shell with exceptionally attenuated sculpture, same locality (H 4.2 mm).

Figura 9. Onchodia tenuicula n. sp. A, B: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, M151/GeoB23112, 599 m (H 3,5 mm) y protoconcha; C, D: concha del Banco Açor, M151/GeoB23139, 339 m (H 3,1 mm) y protoconcha; E, misma localidad, protoconcha de otra concha; F, G: concha del Banco Atlantis, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 2,7 mm) y protoconcha; H, I: concha del Banco Hyères, 480 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 3,4 mm) y protoconcha; J, K: holotipo del Gran Banco Meteor, 470 m, SMT2/DW152 (H 3,3 mm) y protoconcha; L, M: paratipo, misma localidad (H 3,4 mm) y protoconcha; N: paratipo, concha con escultura excepcionalmente atenuada, misma localidad (H 4,2 mm).

Distribution: This recently described species is only known from the type locality, Vitória-Trindade Seamount Chain, 790–1129 m (FERNANDES *ET AL.*, 2015), Hyères and Great Meteor seamounts, 950–1840 m (our material).

Remarks: This species stands out among other *Cerithiella* species in having a coloured protoconch, with distinct protoconch I and protoconch II and a clear-cut limit with teleoconch, indicating a planktotrophic larval development.

Cerithiella metula (Lovén, 1846) (Fig. 11A-E)

Material examined (total 1 specimen and 88 shells): AZORES • 1 shell; Açor Seamount; 38.359°N, 29.051°W; 648 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23135; grab in bioclastic sand • 2 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble • 3 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.642°N, 25.785°W; 613 m; 16 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23163; grab • 1 shell; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.675°N, 25.717°W; 329 m; 06 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23105-2; grab in coral rubble. ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 6 shells; 34.082°N, 30.255°W; 335–340 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW255; dredge • 4 shells; 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge • 18 shells (Fig. 11A-C); 34.373°N, 30.463°W; 1190–1340 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW261; dredge • 1 specimen (juvenile); 34.080°N, 30.2483°W; 330 m; 04 Feb. 1993; SMT2/TS270; suprabenthic sled. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 12 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge • 21 shells; 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge. TYRO SEAMOUNT • 6 shells; 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 32.264°N, 27.531°W; 670–715 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW237; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 31.436°N, 28.863°W; 1520 m; 16 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW186; dredge • 9 shells (Fig. 11D, E); 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW200; dredge • 1 shell; 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan. 1993; 31.158°N, 28.725°W; 845–990 m; 19 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW203; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 29.568°N, 28.340°W; 855 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23425R9; ROV grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble.

Type locality: off Bergen, Norway.

Distribution: Western European margin, from the Barents Sea to the Canaries and into the Mediterranean; Iceland and Mid Atlantic Ridge south to the Azores (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993), Atlantis, Plato, Tyro, Irving, Hyères and Great Meteor seamounts (our material); Western Atlantic from southeastern Greenland to Cape Hatteras, USA (BOUCHET & WARÉN 1993). Depth range usually 100–500 m in the northernmost part of the range, 500–2500 m elsewhere (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993), 329–1520 m in our material.

Remarks: BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) considered *Cerithiella metula* as a widespread and very variable species, including in this variability *Cerithiella macrocephala* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896, described from the Azores. This view has been challenged by HOISAETER (2010) who recognized *Cerithiella danielsseni* as a distinct species confined to deep water with negative temperatu-

res in the Norwegian Sea. Some specimens display an indistinctly duplicated keel, similar to that of *Krachia* spp., surrounding the basal area (our Fig. 11B but also in figure 1296 and others in BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993). Specimens from off Norway, closely resembling *Cerithiella metula* but with a paired keel, were identified as *Krachia cossmanni* by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993: figs 1344–1345) and the radula associated with these specimens (Bouchet & Warén, 1993: fig. 1280) is very different from that of *Cerithiella* (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993: fig. 1275).

The multispiral protoconch of *Cerithiella metula*, with a blurry transition to the teleoconch, does not denote planktotrophic development (see a picture of embryos developing inside the egg capsule in BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993, fig. 1318) and does not display a separable protoconch I and protoconch II stage.

Figure 10. A-E. *Ektonos turbonilloides* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A-C: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 834 m, M151/GeoB23109 (H 5.2 mm), and protoconch; D: shell from Plato Seamount, 1450-1500 m, SMT2/DW250 (H 8.8 mm); note the distorted protoconch; E: same locality, juvenile shell with protoconch. F, G. *Cerithiella candela* Fernandes, Garofalo & Pimenta, 2015. F: shell from Great Meteor Seamount, 1575 m, SMT2/DW180 (H 9.8 mm); G: detail of the protoconch of the same shell, the arrow points to the protoconch-teleoconch limit.

Figura 10. A-E. *Ektonos turbonilloides* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A-C: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, 834 m, M151/GeoB23109 (H 5,2 mm) y protoconcha; D: concha del Banco Plato, 1450-1500 m, SMT2/DW250 (H 8,8 mm; nótese la protoconcha deforme); E: misma localidad, concha juvenil con protoconcha. F, G. *Cerithiella candela* Fernandes, Garofalo & Pimenta, 2015. F: concha del Gran Banco Meteor, 1575 m, SMT2/DW180 (H 9,8 mm); G: detalle de la protoconcha de la misma concha, la flecha señala el límite protoconcha-teleoconcha.

One living specimen (juvenile) could be observed on Atlantis Seamount, collected with a suprabenthic sled. The animal is entirely white, bears two triangular cephalic tentacles, closely set together as in *Cerithiopsis*, and with large black eyes embedded at the base of the tentacles without

bulging. The animal was able to extend the foot quite far outside the aperture when crawling, and to withdraw deeply into the shell leaving the last whorl empty.

The largest shell in our material was collected on Hyères Seamount and measured 10.2 x 2.3 mm.

Cerithiella amblytera (Watson, 1880) (Fig. 11G-I)

Material examined (total 7 shells): ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 2 shells (Fig. 11G, H); 34.373°N, 30.463°W; 1190–1340 m; 03 Feb. 1993, SMT2/DW261; dredge • 1 shell; 33.901°N, 30.155°W; 1220 m; 04 Feb. 1993, SMT2/DW271; dredge. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 11I); 32.289°N, 27.539°W; 890–900 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW238; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 31.425°N, 28.864°W; 950–1250 m; 16 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW185; dredge • 1 shell; 31.284°N, 28.489°W; 1780–1840 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW195; dredge • 1 shell; 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW200; dredge.

Type locality: off Fayal, Azores, 38.633°N, 28.475°W, 450-500 fms (823-914 m) [“Challenger” sta. 75].

Remarks: This species differs from *C. metula* in having only the abapical cord strongly developed, the remainder adapical part of the whorls bearing only smooth axial ribs or bearing only a reduced adapical cord.

Cerithiella seilaeformis n. sp. (Figs. 12A-I)

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Type material (total 10 shells). *Holotype:* LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 12A-D); 29.633°N, 28.967°W; 282 m; 27 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23441; grab in bioclastic sand; MNHN-IM-2000-38576. *Paratypes:* LITTLE METEOR SEAMOUNT • 2 shells (Fig. 12E, F); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38577 • 3 shells; 29.645°N, 28.975°W; 284 m; 27 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23440; grab in bioclastic sand; SMF 359014 • 4 shells; 29.633°N, 28.983°W; 274 m; 27 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23442; grab in bioclastic sand; SMF 359015.

Other material examined (total 4 specimens and 53 shells): ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 34.373°N, 30.463°W; 1190–1340 m; 03 Feb. 1993, SMT2/DW261; dredge. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 1 shell; 32.289°N, 27.539°W; 890–900 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW238; dredge. HYÈRES SEAMOUNT • 12 shells (Fig. 12G-I); 31.387°N, 28.892°W; 480 m; 15 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW182; dredge • 1 shell; 31.425°N, 28.864°W; 950–1250 m; 16 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW185; dredge • 1 shell; 31.318°N, 28.600°W; 1060 m; 18 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW200; dredge. GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 29.750°N, 28.533°W; 319 m; 24 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23419-2; grab in bioclastic sand • 2 shells; 30.166°N, 28.468°W; 325–330 m; 10 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW143; dredge • 4 specimens and 32 shells; 30.033°N, 28.368°W; 470 m; 11 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW152; dredge.

Type locality: Little Meteor Seamount, 29.633°N, 28.967°W, 282 m.

Etymology: The name alludes to the similarity to species of *Seila* A. Adams, 1861.

Description (based on the holotype): Shell medium-sized (H 5.0 mm, W 1.1 mm, Ha 0.77 mm [16% of total height]), with a highly-raised conical spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.48 mm, Wp 0.49 mm) with two whorls, initial whorl obliquely truncated, with a pointed apex, sculpture of 13 strong orthocline ribs per whorl starting from the very beginning. Transition to teleoconch evident by change in sculpture, but not delimited by a sharp line.

(Right page) Figure 11. A-F. *Cerithiella metula* (Lovén, 1846). A-C: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 1190–1340 m, SMT2/DW261 (H 6.7 mm), and protoconch; D: shell from Hyères Seamount, 1060 m, SMT2/DW200 (H 8.7 mm); E: juvenile shell, same locality (H 2.0 mm); F: shell from the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf, 36.056°N, 07.328°W, 903–908 m, Indemares-CHICA0211 cruise sta. DA42 (H 5.1 mm). G-I. *Cerithiella amblytera* (Watson, 1880). G, H: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 1190–1340 m, SMT2/DW261 (H 5.0 mm), and protoconch; I: shell from Irving Seamount, 890 m, SMT2/DW238 (H 6.9 mm).

Figura 11. A-F *Cerithiella metula* (Lovén, 1846). A-C: concha del Banco Atlantis, 1190-1340 m, SMT2/DW261 (H 6,7 mm), y protoconcha; D: concha juvenil del Banco Hyères, 1060 m, SMT2/DW200 (H 8,7 mm); E: misma localidad (H 2,0 mm); F: concha del Golfo Ibero-Marroquí, 36,056°N, 07,328°W, 903-908 m, campaña Indemares-CHICA0211 sta. DA42 (H 5,1 mm). G-I. *Cerithiella amblytera* (Watson, 1880). G, H: concha del Banco Atlantis, 1190 m-1340, SMT2/DW261 (H 5,0 mm) y protoconcha; I: concha del Banco Irving, 890 m, SMT2/DW238 (H 6,9 mm).

Teleoconch with 11 regular whorls, apical angle 8-9° at the beginning of teleoconch, then 10°. Sculpture of spire whorls with three spiral cords of equal strength, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, granulose on the first two whorls, then gradually becoming smooth from the third whorl; median spiral cord equidistant to other cords or slightly closer to abapical one. Numerous fine growth lines, more conspicuous in the interspaces.

Last whorl with two smaller additional spirals, one subperipheral, and a basal one very close to it and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture rhomboidal; flexuous oblique columella, twisted, nearly orthogonal with parietal area, callous thin. Outer lip orthocline, internally smooth with imprint of external sculpture. Short open siphonal canal oblique at about 40° with spire axis in apertural view.

Colour entirely white.

Variability: The shells from Hyères Seamount, and four of the shells from DW152 on Great Meteor Seamount have distinctly beaded spiral cords throughout and could possibly represent a distinct species (Fig. 12G-I). Maximum size is about 5 mm.

Distribution: Great and Little Meteor, Hyères and Irving seamounts, 274-1190 m.

Remarks: *Cerithiella seilaeformis* n. sp. is unique with its combination of an axially sculptured protoconch and smooth spirals on the teleoconch. This species, with its teleoconch sculpture of smooth spiral cords, resembles species of *Seila* A. Adams, 1861 known from the Mediterranean, from West Africa (ROLÁN & FERNANDES, 1990, ROLÁN & PELORCE, 2006) and elsewhere, but all of these possess a smooth protoconch and a weakly developed siphonal canal; we believe that this resemblance does not indicate kinship, but convergence. Conversely, *Cerithiella insignis* (Jeffreys, 1885) (Fig. 12J, K) has a protoconch with similar strong ribs since the very beginning, and therefore may be related, although its apex is more markedly twisted upwards. *Cerithiella sigsbeana* (Dall, 1881), known from the Western Atlantic off Cuba and Brazil (FERNANDES ET AL., 2015), has a similar teleoconch sculpture but is much more slender, brownish in colour and has the first protoconch whorl inflated and smooth.

Genus *Eumetula* Thiele, 1912

Type species: *Eumeta dilecta* Thiele, 1912 by monotypy.

BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) distinguished *Eumetula* from *Cerithiella* on the basis of their very different radulae and,

on shell features, by having a short and widely open siphonal canal, instead of drawn out and less open in *Cerithiella*.

Eumetula bouvieri (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 13A-G)

Material examined (total 65 shells): AZORES • 4 shells; Açor Seamount; 38.359°N, 29.051°W; 648 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23135; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 86317 • 2 shells; José Gaspar Seamount;

(Right page) Figure 12. A-I. *Cerithiella seilaeformis* n. sp. A, B: holotype from Little Meteor Seamount, 282 m, M151/GeoB23441 (H 5.0 mm), and protoconch; C: detail of a median whorl; D: detail of the last whorl; E, F: paratype 1, same locality (H 4.8 mm), and protoconch; G-I: shell from Hyères Seamount, 420 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 4.0 mm), and protoconch. J, K. *Cerithiella insignis* (Jeffreys, 1885), shell from near type locality in Gulf of Cadiz, 36.559°N, 06.932°W, 390 m, cruise Indemares CHICA0610 sta. DA10 (H 2.9 mm), and protoconch.

Figura 12. A-I. *Cerithiella seilaeformis* n. sp. A, B: holotipo del Pequeño Banco Meteor, 282 m, M151/GeoB23441 (H 5,0 mm) y protoconcha; C: detalle de una vuelta mediana; D: detalle de la última vuelta; E, F: paratipo 1, misma localidad (H 4,8 mm) y protoconcha; G-I: concha del Banco Hyères, 420 m, SMT2/DW182 (H 4,0 mm) y protoconcha. J, K. *Cerithiella insignis* (Jeffreys, 1885), concha recolectada cerca de la localidad tipo en el Golfo de Cádiz, 36.559°N, 06.932°W, 390 m, campaña Indemares CHICA0610 sta. DA10 (Al. 2,9 mm), y protoconcha.

37.675°N, 25.717°W; 309 m; 12 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23130; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 87190 • 1 shell; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.676°N, 25.718°W; 293 m; 12 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23131; grab in live coral and rubble; SaM 87191 • 1 shell; José Gaspar Seamount; 37.672°N, 25.713°W; 533 m; 18 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23172; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 87189 • 12 shells (Fig. 13B, C); Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 86308 • 20 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.661°N, 25.918°W; 599 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23112; grab in sand and coral rubble; SaM 86316. ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge • 10 shells (Fig. 13D-G); 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW263; dredge • 4 shells; 33.996°N, 30.177°W; 617 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23408; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 83568. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 9 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge.

Distribution: The distribution of the typical form with beaded ribs includes the Azorean seamounts (DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1896 and our material), Canaries (HERNÁNDEZ *ET AL.* 2011) and Gorringe bank (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993, fig. 1337). Forms with smooth ribs are distributed in Bay of Biscay and on the Galicia Bank (BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993, figs. 1339-1340) in a similar depth range.

Remarks: BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) treated *Eumetula bouvieri* as a widespread, extremely variable species, and selected the shell from the Azores figured by DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1896) as lectotype. The specimens collected on Atlantis and Plato seamounts have the same kind of sculpture as those collected around the Azores, with definite beads at the intersection of axial ribs and spiral cords.

Eumetula fenestrata n. sp. (Fig. 13H-M)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:8FFB2EB3-5269-4FAE-A98A-8805810BAC68

Type material (total 16 shells). *Holotype*: ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 13K, L); 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38578. *Paratypes*: ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 4 shells; 34.082°N, 30.255°W; 335–340 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW255; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38579 • 1 shell; 33.997°N, 30.203°W; 420–460 m; 02 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW258; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38580 • 9 shells (Fig. 13J); 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW263; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38581 • 10 shells; 33.971°N, 30.206°W; 677 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23404; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 83748.

Other material examined (total 32 shells): AZORES • 10 shells (Fig. 13H, I); Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble. TYRO SEAMOUNT • 2 shells; 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 7 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge • 1 shell; 33.210°N, 29.287°W; 1450–1500 m; 01 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW250; dredge. IRVING SEAMOUNT • 2 shells (Fig. 13M); 32.264°N, 27.531°W; 670–715 m; 30 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW237; dredge.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, 33.997°N, 30.203°W, 420–460 m.

Etymology: The name, from Latin *fenestratus*, provided with windows, alludes to the clathrate sculpture formed by the spiral and axial sculpture.

(Right page) Figure 13. A-G. *Eumetula bouvieri* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A: lectotype from the Azores, 454 m, Monaco sta. 234 (H 7.0 mm; reproduced from Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896); B, C: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/23111 (H 6.1 mm), and protoconch; D: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 7.4 mm); E, F: shell from the same locality (H 3.6 mm), and protoconch; G: same locality (H 4.4 mm). H-M. *Eumetula fenestrata* n. sp. H, I: shell from the Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/23111 (5.9 mm); J: shell from Atlantis Seamount, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 6.5 mm); K, L: holotype from Atlantis Seamount, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 4.1 mm), and protoconch; M: shell from Irving Seamount, 670 m, SMT2/DW237 (H 4.8 mm).

Figura 13. A-G. *Eumetula bouvieri* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896). A: lectotipo de las Azores, 454 m, Mónaco sta. 234 (H 7,0 mm); reproducido de Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896); B, C: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/23111 (H 6,1 mm) y protoconcha; D: concha del Banco Atlantis, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 7,4 mm); E, F: concha de la misma localidad (H 3,6 mm) y protoconcha; G: misma localidad (H 4,4 mm). H-M. *Eumetula fenestrata* n. sp. H, I: concha de las Azores, Mar da Prata, 595 m, M151/23111 (H 5,9 mm); J: concha del Banco Atlantis, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 6,5 mm); K, L: holotipo del Banco Atlantis, 420 m, SMT2/DW258 (H 4,1 mm) y protoconcha; M: concha del Banco Irving, 670 m, SMT2/DW237 (H 4,8 mm).

Description (based on the juvenile holotype): Shell small (H 4.1 mm, W 1.4 mm, Ha 0.74 mm [18% of height]), with a raised, somewhat cyrtocoenoid spire.

Protoconch (Hp 0.65 mm, Wp 0.65 mm) pupoid, of ca. 2.5 whorls, apical angle ca. 30°, nearly equal in width to the first teleoconch whorl. First ½ whorl small and smooth, convex; following 2 whorls convex with 9-10 curved, opisthocline axial ribs on each whorl. Transition to teleoconch not clearly demarcated.

Teleoconch with 5 ½ regular convex whorls, apical angle 15° in early whorls, decreasing to ca. 10°; sculpture of about 14 orthocline, regularly-spaced axial ribs with slightly larger interspaces, and 3 smaller spiral cords overrunning the ribs. Interspaces between cords larger than width of cords, and largest between upper suture and adapical cord.

Last whorl with an additional (sub-peripheral) cord, delimiting a slightly concave basal area with only growth lines and an inconspicuous spiral cordlet close to the columella. Aperture nearly rounded. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocline, internally smooth with imprint of external sculpture. Parietal area slightly concave. Columella vertical, flexuous. Siphonal canal very short, widely open, slightly twisted outward.

Colour whitish.

Variability: Little variability observed; maximum height up to 7 mm with

up to 7 teleoconch whorls. On larger shells and, a swelling under the suture forms a very inconspicuous subsutural cord.

Distribution: Tyro, Plato, Irving and Atlantis seamounts; Azores (Mar da Prata), 335–1500 m.

Remarks: *Eumetula fenestrata* n. sp. is found sympatrically with *E. bouvieri* on Atlantis and Plato seamounts and consistently distinguished by the spiral cords narrower than their interspaces and not forming beads at their intersection with the cords. Morphs of *E. bouvieri* with attenuated beads (e.g. BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993, fig. 1338) are less obviously different but the protoconch is consistently different, being pupoid with three whorls and a pointed apex in *E. fenestrata* n. sp. instead of globose with less than two whorls. The Western Atlantic *Eumetula vitrea* (Dall, 1927) is the most similar species and its protoconch was described by DALL (1927) as “turban-shaped, larger than the succeeding whorl”; however the holotype illustrated by FERNANDES ET AL. 2015 (p. 800, fig. 8 b-c) shows a teleoconch sculpture with two widely separated spiral cordlets and an indistinct spiral sculpture in between, which give the ribs a biangulated profile, whereas in *E. fenestrata* the three spirals are equivalent in strength and form the clathrate sculpture with the ribs.

Eumetula alicei (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896) (Fig. 14A, B)

Material examined: GREAT METEOR SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 14A, B); 29.568°N, 28.340°W; 855 m; 25 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23425R9; ROV grab in bioclastic sand with coral rubble; SaM 84858.

Remarks: Recent *Eumetula alicei* is only known from the holotype off the Azores, Monaco sta. 578, 38.433°N, 26.517°W, 1165 m and one fragmentary shell in this study from the Great Meteor Seamount. It was also recorded from Pliocene and Pleistocene deposits of Italy (MONI & TABANELLI, 2004 and

references therein; BOUCHET & WARÉN, 1993: 605). BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) emended the specific name to *aliceae* because it should have been so construed following ICZN Art. 31.1.2, but under Art. 32.5, such an incorrect formation does not justify the emendation.

Figure 14. A, B. *Eumetula alicei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), shell from Great Meteor Seamount, 855 m, M151/23425R9 (H 3.7 mm). C-F. *Eumetula bicarinata* n. sp. C: holotype from Atlantis Seamount, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 4.2 mm); D-F: paratype from Atlantis Seamount, 677 m, M151/23404 (H 3.8 mm), and protoconch. G-I. *Eumetula* cf. *bicarinata* n. sp., shell from the Azores, Açor Seamount, 648 m, M151/23135 (H 2.7 mm), and protoconch.
 Figura 14. A, B. *Eumetula alicei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), concha del Gran Banco Meteor, 855 m, M151/23425R9 (H 3,7 mm). C-F. *Eumetula bicarinata* n. sp. C: holotipo del Banco Atlantis, 610 m, SMT2/DW263 (H 4,2 mm); D-F: paratipo del Banco Atlantis, 677 m, M151/23404 (H 3,8 mm) y protoconcha. G-I. *Eumetula* cf. *bicarinata* n. sp., concha de las Azores, Banco Açor, 648 m, M151/23135 (H 2,7 mm) y protoconcha.

Eumetula bicarinata n. sp. (Fig. 14C-I)

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Type material (total 4 shells): *Holotype*: ATLANTIS SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 14C); 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW263; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38582. *Paratypes*: ATLANTIS

SEAMOUNT • 1 shell (Fig. 13D-F); 33.971°N, 30.206°W; 677 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23404; grab in bioclastic sand; MNHN-IM-2000-38583 • 2 shells; 33.996°N, 30.177°W; 617 m; 21 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23408; grab in bioclastic sand; SMF 359016 • 2 shells; 34.373°N, 30.463°W; 1190–1340 m; 03 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW261; dredge; MNHN-IM-2000-38584.

Other material examined (total 14 shells): AZORES • 2 shells (identified as *Eumetula* cf. *bicarinata* n. sp.; Fig. 13G-I); Açor Seamount; 38.359°N, 29.051°W; 648 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23135; grab in bioclastic sand; SaM 86314. PLATO SEAMOUNT • 3 shells; 33.197°N, 28.949°W; 690–710 m; 31 Jan. 1993; SMT2/DW242; dredge. TYRO SEAMOUNT • 9 shells; s; 33.963°N, 28.373°W; 890–925 m; 06 Feb. 1993; SMT2/DW278; dredge.

Type locality: Atlantis Seamount, 34.432°N, 30.542°W; 610–655 m.

Etymology: *bicarinata* refers to the two projecting spiral cords on each whorl of the teleoconch.

Description (based on holotype): Shell small (H 4.2 mm, W 0.9 mm, Ha = 0.55 mm [13% of height]), with a highly raised conical outline.

Protoconch (Hp 0.45 mm; Wp 0.42 mm) of about 1 ½ whorl, the first one smooth, the next half-whorl with ca. 15 opisthocline, slightly curved axial ribs. The transition to the teleoconch is unclear, marked only by the appearance of a spiral cord.

Teleoconch with 9 whorls, slightly convex, slowly but regularly increasing in diameter, apical angle rather constant at 8–9°. Sculpture with two strong, elevated median and abapical cords, smoothly rounded, and a third, less conspicuous adapical cordlet just below the suture. Fine, slightly opisthocline axial riblets, narrower than interspaces, more than 40 per whorl on the last whorls.

Last whorl with an additional sub-peripheral spiral cord, similar to the two other cords and delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Aperture subquadrangular, with

union of lip with penultimate whorl at 90°. Outer lip thin, convex, orthocline, internally smooth. Columella vertical. Siphonal canal short, widely open, slightly twisted outward.

Colour white.

Variability: Adult size is observed as 4.0–4.5 mm. The shells from the Açor Seamount are more coarsely ribbed and have a more pointed protoconch.

Distribution: Azores (Açor Seamount), Atlantis, Plato and Tyro seamounts, 610–890 m.

Remarks: This species is here tentatively placed in *Eumetula* because it most resembles *Eumetula alicei* (Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1896), placed in that genus by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) on the grounds that the siphonal canal is not drawn out as in *Cerithiella*. *Eumetula alicei* differs in having only one spiral keel, placed on the abapical part of the spire whorls. The sculpture of the teleoconch is reminiscent of that of the protoconch of *Cerithiopsis atalaya* Watson, 1885 and *C. slikeri* n. sp.

Genus *Trituba* Jousseau, 1884

Type species *Triforis bitubulata* Baudon, 1856 †, by monotypy.

Trituba azorica n. sp. (Fig. 15A-I)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:EE9E10BB-7ED5-4470-BCB6-2B46FCEBE4A5

Type material (total 70 shells): *Holotype:* AZORES • 1 shell (Fig. 15A, B); José Gaspar Seamount; 37.675°N, 25.717°W; 329 m; 06 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23105-2; grab in coral rubble; MNHN-IM-2000-38585. *Paratypes:* AZORES • 3 shells; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-38586 • 7 shells (Fig. 15C-I); same data as for holotype; SMF 359017 • 8 shells; 37.676°N, 25.718°W; 293 m; 12 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23131; grab in live coral and rubble; SaM 86323 • 51 shells; 37.675°N, 25.7166°W; 311 m; 16 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23161; box-core in live coral and rubble; SaM 85086.

Figure 15. *Trituba azorica* n. sp. from the Azores, José Gaspar Seamount, 329 m, M151/GeoB23105. A, B: holotype (H 7.6 mm); C, D: paratype 1 (H 5.7 mm), and protoconch; E: detail of the last whorl showing anal canal; F: paratype 2 in apical view; G, H: paratype 3 (H 5.0 mm), and protoconch; I: detail of the last whorl.

Figura 15. Trituba azorica n. sp. de las Azores, Banco José Gaspar, 329 m, M151/GeoB23105. A, B: holotipo, (H 7,6 mm); C, D: paratipo 1 (H 5,7 mm) y protoconcha; E: detalle de la última vuelta mostrando el canal anal; F: paratipo 2 en vista apical; G, H: paratipo 3 (H 5,0 mm) y protoconcha; I: detalle de la última vuelta.

Other material examined (total 115 shells): AZORES • 6 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.669°N, 25.926°W; 834 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23109; grab, coral rubble • 79 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.673°N, 25.925°W; 595 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23111; grab, sand and coral rubble • 19 shells; Mar da Prata; 37.661°N, 25.918°W; 599 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23112; grab in sand and coral rubble • 1 shell; 37.669°N, 25.906°W; 406 m; 08 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23114; grab, sand and coral rubble • 1 shell; Mar da Prata; 37.644°N, 25.781°W; 610 m; 16 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23162; box-core in bioclastic sand • 1 shell; Açor Seamount; 38.359°N, 29.051°W; 648 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23135; grab in bioclastic sand • 8 shells; Açor Seamount; 38.156°N, 29.064°W; 339 m; 13 Oct. 2018; M151/GeoB23139; grab in coral rubble.

Type locality: Azores, off SW São Miguel, José Gaspar Seamount, 37.675°N, 25.717°W, 329 m.

Etymology: *azorica* refers to the type locality, Azores.

Description (based on the holotype): Shell medium-sized (H 7.6 mm, W 2.4 mm, Ha 1.1 mm [14% of total height]), with highly-raised conical spire

Protoconch (Hp 0.77 mm, Wp 0.63 mm) raised, multispiral; first whorl

well-rounded, smooth, diameter 0.23 mm; following 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ convex regularly growing whorls, with large straight ribs, initially with 13 orthocone ribs, last whorl with 13 oblique, opisthocline ribs. Transition to teleoconch evident by

change in sculpture, but not delimited by a sharp line.

Teleoconch with 12 regular whorls, apical angle about 15°. Sculpture of spire whorls with two spiral cords, the abapical one stronger on early whorls, of equal strength on last whorl, overrun by smooth, oblique, 16-17 opisthocline axial ribs per whorl forming strong nodules at intersections. .

Last whorl with a strong subperipheral cord, delimiting a smooth, concave basal area with fine growth lines. Axial ribs and spiral cords fade away towards lip. Aperture (Fig. 15I) rounded with a nearly continuous peristome, a closed siphonal canal (diameter 0.38 mm) oblique at 5-25° in apertural view (Fig. 15A, B), about 50° to coiling axis in lateral view, and a closed anal canal (diameter 0.32 mm), protruding laterally, slightly upwards. Inside of aperture smooth, with a slit running towards siphonal canal. Opening of anal and siphonal canals connected by a suture to the edge of the peristome. Columella nearly straight, orthogonal with parietal area

Colour white, shell material somewhat translucent.

Variability: The elaborate aperture is seen only on adult shells, whereas juveniles have a thin, simple outer lip and an open siphonal canal. Shell outline is conical to slightly cyrtoconoidal. The number of axial ribs is 15-19 per whorl. The oblique angle of the siphonal canal is variable. Sub-adult specimens show

an obliquely twisted open siphonal canal and have an inconspicuous open anal canal at the union with the penultimate whorl. The adult stage with the closed siphonal and anal canals takes place at any size from a height of at least 4 mm. Maximum size from old shells is about 13 mm.

Distribution: Azorean seamounts (Mar da Prata, José Gaspar Seamount, Açor Seamount), 293-834 m.

Remarks: *Trituba azorica* n. sp. is similar to *Trituba hirta* Gofas, 2003 from the Atlantis Seamount, however this species is smaller, with a vertical siphonal canal and a similar protoconch with 2 ½ whorls as opposed to 3 ¾ whorls in the new species, which has oblique siphonal and anal canals. Other similar species discussed by GOFAS (2003) include *Trituba superstes* (Bouchet and Warén, 1982), *Trituba fallax* Gofas, 2003, *Trituba additicia* Gofas, 2003, and *Trituba elatissima* Gofas, 2003, but all these species have a slightly different sculpture of teleoconch and protoconch, and all their siphonal canals are short and vertical. BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993, fig. 1360) figured a protoconch of *Trituba azorica* n. sp. from the campaign Monaco sta. 112, but did not describe it. Empty shells of *Trituba azorica* n. sp. have been found in bioclastic sediment; numerous live sponges from various genera have been found near the sampling locations, but not a single live specimen has been found so far.

DISCUSSION

The 21 species (discounting the unidentified *Krachia* spp.) reported herein are represented by a total of 882 shells and only 5 live-taken specimens. Most species are present on more than one of the seamounts and/or around the Azores archipelago (Table I). Ten species (half of the total 21) are only known from upper bathyal depths on the Azorean and/or South Azorean seamounts and they are currently considered as endemic. Three species (15%; possibly 4 with *Ektonos* cf. *turbonilloides* reported by

FERNANDES ET AL. 2021 from the Rio Grande Rise) are known from the Western Atlantic and 9 species (45%) are known from the continental slopes in the NE Atlantic. The most widespread species is *Cerithiella metula*, which is present on all the investigated sites and is amphiatlantic. However, *Onchodia tenuicula* n. sp. also occurs throughout the seamount chain and the Azores, although it is endemic to the area. At the other extreme, *Trituba azorica* n. sp. is restricted to the Mar da Prata and Açor

Table I. Distribution of species herein studied of Cerithiopsidae and Newtoniellidae encountered on the Azores and the South Azorean seamounts. “N” indicates the total number of shell and specimens; “1” denotes presence of a species; “*” indicates the type locality; “cf.” indicates a morphological deviation from the type material. Development can be P, planktonic or N, non-planktonic. n° Loc: number of sites in the study area. New species are indicated in bold.

Tabla I. Distribución de especies en Cerithiopsidae y Newtoniellidae encontradas en las Azores y los montes submarinos al sur del archipiélago. N indica el número total de conchas y especímenes; “1” denota la presencia de una especie; “*” indica la localidad tipo; “cf.” indica una desviación morfológica del material tipo. El desarrollo puede ser P, planctónico o N, no planctónico. N^a Loc: número de sitios en el área de estudio. Las especies nuevas se indican en negrita.

	N	W. Atlantic	Azores	Atlantis	Plato	Tyro	Irving	Hyères	Meteor	Canaries / Madeira	W. Europe	development	n° Loc
<i>Cerithiopsis fayalensis</i>	15		1*	1		1			1	1	1	P	4
<i>Cerithiopsis slikeri</i>	14		1*		1				1		cf.	P	3
<i>Cerithiopsis minima</i>	4		1						1	1	1	P	2
<i>Cerithiopsis diadema</i>	5		1							1	1	P	1
<i>Krachia guernei</i>	1		1					1				N	2
<i>Krachia obeliscoides</i>	10		1					1			1*	N	2
<i>Krachia cochleapex</i>	87			cf.	1*			cf.				N	3
<i>Krachia trauseli</i>	37		1*									N	1
<i>Krachia stilapex</i>	33			1*	1	1	1	1	1			N	6
<i>Krachia meteoris</i>	13				1			cf.	1*			N	3
<i>Onchodia tenuicula</i>	167		1	1	1		1	1	1*			N	6
<i>Ektonos turbonilloides</i>	15	cf.	1		1						1	N	2
<i>Cerithiella candela</i>	7	1*						1	1			P	2
<i>Cerithiella metula</i>	85	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1*	N	7
<i>Cerithiella amblytera</i>	6	1	1*	1			1					N	3
<i>Cerithiella seilaeformis</i>	67			1			1	1	1*			N	4
<i>Eumetula bouvieri</i>	65		1*	1	1					1	cf.	N	3
<i>Eumetula fenestrata</i>	47		1	1*	1	1	1					N	5
<i>Eumetula alicei</i>	1		1*						1			N	2
<i>Eumetula bicarinata</i>	18		1	1*		1						N	3
<i>Trituba azorica</i>	185		1*									N	1

Seamount near the Azores, and *Krachia trauseli* n. sp. is restricted to the Azores.

Multispiral protoconchs, as evidenced by BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) for *Cerithiella metula*, do not imply planktotrophic development unless a protoconch I and protoconch II are clearly differentiated (see also FERNANDES & PIMENTA, 2019). As a difference with classical planktotrophic protoconchs, most cerithiellid protoconchs feature globose nucleus, a blurred transition

from protoconch to teleoconch, and a high phenotypic plasticity. Endemism should be a consequence: sixteen of the recorded species have a non-planktonic larval development and 10 species (63%) in this set are restricted to the Azorean seamounts. Conversely, five species (24%) likely have a planktotrophic development and all these species have a wide distribution area extending to the continental slopes of the NE and/or the West Atlantic Ocean.

Most of the species (with the exception of the shallow water *Cerithiopsis*) have a whitish teleoconch, which is a common feature in the bathyal environment. Among those, the species with a planktotrophic larval development (*Cerithiopsis* cf. *fayalensis*, *C. slikeri*, *Cerithiella candela*) have a brown protoconch reflecting the planktonic stage spent in superficial waters of the photic zone (BOUCHET, 1976). Whether the presence of a colour pattern in the teleoconch is a reliable species-specific character is unclear. We tentatively referred specimens with a whitish teleoconch to *Cerithiopsis fayalensis*, which is brown in adult stage when occurring in the photic zone. Nevertheless, we have observed several cases [e.g. the rissoid *Alvania testae* (Aradas and Maggiore, 1844), the columbellid *Amphissa acutecostata* (Philippi, 1844)] where the same species are white in deep-water and have a colour pattern in shallower environments. Conversely, we have treated as distinct the non-planktotrophic *Krachia trauseli* from the Azores and *K. meteoris* from the South Azorean seamounts because they occur in similar depth ranges (234–834 m vs. 470–565 m) and nevertheless constantly differ in being banded vs. white.

The number of sites where a species was found shows no clear relation to species abundance, nor to larval development. The two most abundant species are *Trituba azorica* n. sp. (185 shells), present only around the Azores, and *Onchodia tenuicula* n. sp. (167 shells), present in all six sites displayed in Table I.

Krachia and *Trituba* appear more prone than others to seamount-to-seamount isolation. GOFAS (2003) provided a nearly complete inventory of Recent species of *Trituba* in the NE Atlantic; all hitherto known species are endemic to the Azorean seamounts. This study yielded one more species (*Trituba azorica* n. sp.) endemic to the seamounts near the Azores, extending the specific radiation further North than initially

observed. *Krachia* also differentiated into distinct species along the South Azorean Seamount Chain, as well as differences which could be intraspecific among distinct populations of *Krachia cochleapex* n. sp. This raises the question whether more congeneric species are to be found on seamounts around the Azores or on the nearby Mid Atlantic Ridge: the single shells of *Krachia* spp. which could not be assigned to any of the described species strongly suggest that more species are to be found.

Despite the fact that the NE Atlantic fauna has been intensely studied for about 200 years, relatively few bathyal species have been described in the Triphoroidea except for BOUCHET & FECHTER (1981), BOUCHET & WARÉN (1993) and GOFAS (2003). This study is based on the morphology of empty shells only, which is quite common for oceanic seamounts where bioclasts are the main source of sediment. A more reliable taxonomic classification will be possible when molecular analyses become available.

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